

Business-to-consumer e-commerce in casual dining restaurants in Bacoor amidst COVID-19 pandemic

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Abstract

January 2020 when COVID-19 shocked the world and many hospitality businesses were affected, especially restaurants. People chose to stay at home rather than dine in. This study focused on how restaurants survived in the midst of the pandemic with the help of technology. It also discussed that business-to-consumer e-commerce plays a big role in restaurants in this situation and how they adapted B2C e-commerce platforms to overcome these challenges. With the research questions being the center focus, the researchers picked 105 staff members of casual dining restaurants in Bacoor to find out how they adjusted to B2C e-commerce platforms. The researchers used online platforms such as Facebook/Messenger and email to conduct the survey. The results were sought, and it helped the researchers to properly identify how the restaurants adapt to B2C e-commerce platforms. Based on the findings, technology helps restaurants survive this pandemic which allowed them to sustain their businesses. The B2C e-commerce platform has a positive impact on the restaurant industry, and it helps them to survive despite the COVID-19 pandemic. The use of the different B2C e-commerce platforms gives benefits to the casual dining restaurants as well as the customers in Bacoor. Future researchers can make use of the result of this research as one of their sources when conducting related or similar research that can make a greater contribution in the field of the hospitality industry.

Keywords: *Delivery; digital adoption; B2C e-commerce; COVID-19 pandemic; restaurants.*

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Introduction

The Coronavirus Disease 2019 or COVID-19 made a devastating impact on the health of many, making it the primary concern for all people. Human health has been the most visible and tragic victim of the pandemic ever since it started (Huang et al., 2020). Each new case announced causes a domino effect on the economy. The pandemic appears to have shifted some people's perspectives as most of them became more health-conscious during this period. Health protocols have become tightly regulated that everyone must follow them, including those who want to start a business. It is also one of the challenges of hospitality management. The restaurant industry must ensure that everyone including employees and customers wears protective equipment, follow social distancing, and show proof that they are virus-free since the industry involves more face-to-face interaction with different types of people.

Multiple countries across the globe have weakened economically which resulted in the temporary inactivity of many hospitality businesses and a decrease in demand. Over 50% of the population is not willing to dine at a restaurant and stay at hotels. The same goes for people who contemplate traveling and staying at a hotel. However, as the health protocols have loosened their safety guidelines, some customers chose to dine in restaurants, and some are now willing to travel and stay at a hotel (Gursoy et al., 2020; Gursoy & Chi, 2020). This change in consumers' behavior has been going on for a long time. The uncertainties of this pandemic bother the consumers as well as the question of stability in this kind of time.

Foroudi et al. (2021) stated that the hospitality industry must be innovative to guarantee customers will receive safe products and services. The authors added that the sectors need to support customers' self-protection by providing minimum health protocols. They must also reassure customers that the destination or place of visit is safe, which could help the industry build trust and relationships with its customers.

The pandemic that the world continues to experience has accelerated the events that will affect the daily lives of everyone. The crisis has hampered people's ability to go outside and has expedited the adoption of digital technologies specifically business-to-customer e-commerce. From acquiring necessities to working, a growing number of people are relying on digital platforms. The progression of the pandemic and the restriction of dine-in services became a roadmap for businesses in looking for ways to revive even though COVID-19 affects their revenue, particularly restaurants. Jun et al. (2021) stated that to be competitive, restaurants should fully employ online food delivery platforms in providing service to their clients, as online platforms are widely used by customers today. Globally, online food delivery has grown at an astonishing rate in recent years, and it is critical in reviving the restaurant industry (Tran, 2021). Even after the pandemic, it is expected that the number of customers and restaurants using online food delivery services will increase.

The researchers understand that the hospitality industry needs to adjust to the new needs of the customers. It indicates that it is difficult to return to the normal way of living immediately, thus necessitating the implementation of new methods and protocols based on the experience brought by COVID-19. The factors that influence the increased digital adoption amidst the pandemic are perceived usefulness, managerial support, peers, social network, and prior experience. First, the subjective view of users that employing particular technologies can improve their work performance is known as perceived usefulness. Second, managerial assistance is a type of successful communication between workers and managers that includes including workers in crucial decisions, providing clear feedback on their performance, and assisting them with tough jobs to achieve better results. Third, the peers want to adopt a specific behavior, appearance, or attitude to be accepted as a member of a group of individuals. Fourth, content, images, promotions, discounts, and influencers all play a role in the social network's potential to influence customer purchasing behavior. Lastly, the prior experience. It is about making decisions that people might have made before that can be used in the present. One example would be a person who used gadgets before in ordering foods online even though the pandemic has not occurred yet.

Overall, this study provides valuable findings that might be useful for every restaurant to make adjustments on how they cope with the new normal setting. In the process of doing the study, the researchers can utilize the findings to present the business-to-customer e-commerce in casual dining restaurants and identify the adjustments and actions that need to be taken in order to survive the pandemic.

Increased Digital Adoption

The current situation is a global health phenomenon that has affected everyone's lives. The increasing number of cases of the COVID-19 virus changes the landscape of the hospitality industry. It leads to several of its businesses closing temporarily, if not permanently. It also changes the way their customers behave during this crisis. Due to the pandemic, everyone's mobility becomes limited to minimize the spread of the virus. Since then, consumers have spent most of their time at home and have accelerated digital adoption. Their homes are transformed into workplaces. The online platform became a replacement for face-to-face interactions, as customers utilized it for social, business, and educational purposes (Afridi et al., 2021). Furthermore, with their embrace of digital technologies during this crisis, there is a surge in online sales as customers purchase their necessities through online platforms more often than usual (Akker et al., 2021).

The coronavirus disease brought pain to the world's economies. Travel agencies, hotels, and restaurants took a heavy blow during this period, as the operation of these businesses became restricted when quarantine started. The COVID-19 pandemic cost the global economy approximately \$3.5 trillion (Sentance, 2021). However, the crisis has led to the rise of business-to-consumer e-commerce, which has become a prominent tool during this era. Electronic commerce, or e-commerce, is a platform for selling goods and services over the internet, either through a computer, mobile device, or another digital platform (Alfonso et al., 2021). Since the pandemic has weakened the economies of all countries, it has made them rely on e-commerce as an alternative source of income to revive the declining economy. As a result, there is an increase in the economy in the part of electronic commerce that involves several businesses using e-commerce platforms to increase their revenue during this crisis. This occurrence happens due to the customers' avoidance of purchasing products outside of their homes to avoid a spike in coronavirus cases (Khuluqo & Hikmat, 2022).

According to Rizvi (2021), the pandemic has accelerated the shift to online shopping, increased the need for omnichannel, and caused substantial changes in consumer buying habits. The amount of time many people will spend watching television has increased for the first time in ten years, and there is a growing demand for digital wellness as individuals choose to stay at home and deal with greater stress and mental health awareness. Reading news and engaging in hobbies are also taking up more time. Consumers nowadays rely on digital for communication, education, and coping with anxiety and depression. As the pandemic progresses, more and more people are becoming accustomed to working from home.

Sheth (2020) observed that consumers have embraced new digital technology and applications out of necessity. The technology's impact to the general and social media is immense and widespread in the lives of everyday consumers. For customers worldwide, the COVID-19 pandemic has created a new reality. Users of digital technology have had to adapt and apply certain technologies to cope (Erjavec & Manfreda, 2022).

One of the rapid changes imposed by lockdowns is the rising use of various digital technologies such as internet-based services for communicating, engaging, and working from home. Organizations have also embraced digital technology more quickly, with three to four years of faster digitization of customer and supply chain interactions and seven years of more rapid digitization in sharing through digital platforms (LaBerge et al., 2020).

According to Liew et al. (2017), there is a significant gap between consumer acceptance and corporate adoption. They define technology adoption as the act of a person, a corporation, or another agency making the initial use of a new piece of equipment or software. In this setting, technological advancements can lead to the introduction of ground-breaking new goods, services, and managerial practices. Utilizing real-world examples from information technology adoption, the writers underlined the importance of prices, benefits, communication networks, and other complicated elements in implementing new technology.

E-commerce

Victor (2019) stated that e-commerce is a platform used to sell and buy products with the help of the internet. However, it is essential to remember that not all online transactions involve the use of e-commerce. E-commerce is a broad term with several subcategories, which are as follows: Business-to-Business, Business-to-Consumer, Consumer-to-Business, and Consumer-to-Consumer.

Business-to-business e-commerce is a type of e-commerce that facilitates the trade of products, information, or services between two businesses (Hashemi-Pour, n.d.). Transactions take place on a variety of websites, such as corporate websites, product supply, and procurement exchanges, specialized or vertical industry portals, brokering sites, and information sites. Business-to-business is critical since it necessitates acquiring products and services from other businesses to grow. It also operates in several industries, one of which is food and beverage.

Faiz et al. (2021) explained that business-to-consumer are the common types of e-commerce where businesses sell their products or services directly to consumers. It also pertains to using online platforms to connect products to the consumer (Essex, 2016). An example of this type is dining out in a restaurant and using apps to order food. In consumer-to-business, the consumer gives service to the business, in which the consumer plays the role of a seller while the business act as a buyer (Victor, 2019).

Customers can connect to companies that allow them to offer their services via the internet in this type of e-commerce. Sanfilippo (2022) stated that an example is influencers that businesses can reach out to and pay with money to make a video like a blog or paid advertisement about their product. In addition, consumer-to-business is not limited to influencers, but also to affiliate marketing, freelance, contractors, and gig workers. Consumer-to-consumer refers to online transactions between consumers with the assistance of a third party such as eBay, Etsy, and Fivver (Zande, 2020).

Research Objectives

- To determine the views of high-ranking employees on the use of business-to-consumer e-commerce platforms.
- To determine how business-to-consumer e-commerce helps casual dining restaurants to cope and survive during the pandemic.
- To provide valuable findings for future research.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to provide valuable results that reflect on business-to-consumer e-commerce in casual dining restaurants amidst the pandemic. Specifically, this study seeks to find answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the following?
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
2. How do the respondents assess digital adoption amidst the COVID-19 pandemic?
3. How does the restaurant industry cope with the effects of COVID-19 with the help of technology?
4. How does e-commerce contribute to the survival of the restaurant industry during the pandemic?

5. What improvements can restaurants make to attract more customers with the use of business-to-consumer e-commerce?

Significance of the Study

This study shows that business-to-consumer e-commerce is one of the most important for business owners. Conducting this study will help readers understand the changes in restaurant approach, behaviors brought by the pandemic, and the factors of increased digital adoption that leads to B2C e-commerce reliance in this time of the pandemic. It will be helpful in every market to utilize the information about changes for marketing opportunities.

Consumers – this study can help consumers be aware of what platforms restaurants offer in this time of pandemic and what they can expect with the service of casual dining restaurants in Bacoor.

Restaurant Owners – this study can help them to improve and develop their ways to accommodate and keep their customers. The study can also give information on what services are effective that they can offer with the help of business-to-consumer e-commerce.

Future Researchers – this study will guide future researchers to have background knowledge about this kind of study. They will use this as their reference if they plan to conduct the same type of study while exploring a bit more using different methods.

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive design was applied in this study. Therefore, the researchers have prepared questions that would give light and connection to what is being studied in digital adoption in terms of business-to-consumer e-commerce in casual dining restaurants in Bacoor, and how it was relevant to the respondents during the COVID-19 pandemic. High-ranking employees of casual dining restaurants in Bacoor City, Cavite have heterogeneous demographics that responded differently to other variables, making the research approach descriptive research.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Bacoor City, Cavite, where the target respondents work. The researchers focused on casual dining restaurants around Bacoor, and local high-ranking employees were a perfect fit.

Sampling Procedures

The researchers used simple random sampling. Based on our criteria, managers and supervisors are the best respondents. Each branch of different casual dining restaurants has two to three branch managers and one supervisor that have an equal chance of being selected. A total number of 105 respondents were the focus of the study and their age and gender play a big role in the results. Other factors such as employment status, civil status, income, and family size were not considered in this study other than noting the overall demographic of the respondents.

Instruments

The researchers used an adopted online survey questionnaire for this quantitative research and was adopted from the study of Sultana and Islam (2020) which is the “*Role of E-commerce for the Survival of Food Service Industry during COVID-19.*” The questionnaire was validated and tested for reliability. The questionnaire comprises two (2) demographic questions and twenty (20) survey questions for each research question. In addition, the researchers conducted a pilot test of the instrument, which yielded a Cronbach alpha of 0.94.

Data Collection

An online survey has been conducted by the researchers due to the current situation brought by the pandemic. Researchers decided to settle with the said procedure because it is more convenient and safe for both researchers and respondents than traditional data gathering and printed questionnaires. The online survey form is sent to the respondents via email and Facebook Messenger.

Data Analysis Procedure

The data gathered using the research instrument given to 105 respondents were then tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted by the researchers. The researchers used all the gathered data to construct a reliable discussion in order to formally conclude the results. For research question #1, frequency and percentage were used. For research questions #2 to 4, percentages and means with verbal interpretation were used. The range is as follows: 4.21-5.00 = 5 (Strongly Agree); 3.41-4.20 = 4 (Agree); 2.61-3.40 = 3 (Neutral); 1.81-2.60 = 2 (Disagree); and 1.00-1.80 = 1 (Strongly Disagree).

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents (n=105)

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	61	58%
	Male	43	41%
	Transgender	1	1%
Age	18-24	42	40%
	25-31	38	37%
	32-38	13	12%
	39 and above	12	11%

According to the data shown above, the majority of participants, 42 high ranking employees, or roughly 40% of the total, are between the ages of 18 and 24. The majority of respondents working in Bacoor's casual dining restaurants were from Generation Z. The table also shows that most of the respondents to this survey were female, aged approximately 61 (58%). There were only 43 (41%) males and only 1 (1%) transgender who responded to this survey. According to the data, most females prefer to work in casual dining establishments.

Table 2. Assessment of respondents to digital adoption

Statements	Weighted Mean (N=105)	Verbal Interpretation
1. Ordering online makes customers feel secure.	3.88	Agree
2. Having knowledge about business-to-consumer e-commerce or online orders is a must.	4.47	Strongly Agree
3. Food delivery service is more valued now than ever.	4.31	Strongly Agree
4. The use of B2C e-commerce in the restaurant industry will increase in the future.	4.37	Strongly Agree
5. Online purchase is more convenient than the traditional method.	4.12	Agree

According to table 2, respondents strongly agreed with statement number 2: “*having knowledge about business-to-consumer e-commerce or online orders is a must*” with a weighted mean of 4.47. In statement 4, “*the use of B2C e-commerce in the restaurant industry will increase in the future*” respondents strongly agreed with a weighted mean of 4.37. Respondents strongly agreed in statement 3 “*food delivery service is more valued now than ever*” with a weighted mean of 4.31. In statement 5, “*online purchase is more convenient than the traditional method*” respondents agreed with a weighted mean of 4.12. In statement number 1, “*ordering online makes customers feel secure*” respondents strongly agreed with a weighted mean of 3.88.

Table 3. Ways of the restaurant industry in coping with the effects of COVID-19

Statements	Weighted Mean (N=105)	Verbal Interpretation
1. Selling through the internet requires low expenditure.	3.94	Agree
2. Contactless payments are more convenient than cash.	4.36	Strongly Agree
3. Social media presence built ways to boost the restaurant.	4.60	Strongly Agree
4. In order to cope with the pandemic, users of digital technology have to embrace and use particular technologies.	4.44	Strongly Agree
5. The restaurant is able to provide the demand of online ordering and delivery.	4.37	Strongly Agree

According to table 3, respondents strongly agreed with statement number 4: “*In order to cope with the pandemic, users of digital technology have to embrace and use particular technologies.*” with a weighted mean of 4.44. In statement 2, “*Contactless payments are more convenient than cash*” respondents strongly agreed with a weighted mean of 4.36. Respondents strongly agreed with statement 3 “*Social media presence built ways to boost the restaurant*” with a weighted mean of 4.60. In statement 4, “*The restaurant is able to provide the demand of online ordering and delivery*” with a weighted mean of 4.37. In statement 5, “*The restaurant is able to provide the demand of online ordering and delivery*” respondents agreed with a weighted mean of 4.37.

In table 4, respondents strongly agreed in statements 2 and 6 “*online market adoption is helpful for restaurants in this pandemic*” and “*it is important to recruit an employee that is flexible enough to do any task*” respectively with a weighted mean of 4.54. In statement 3, “*there is a significant difference between online and physical sales in terms of dealing with the customers*” respondents strongly agreed with a weighted mean of 4.53. Respondents strongly agreed with statement 4, “*there is a substantial change in the restaurant’s revenue in using digital technology*” with a weighted mean of 4.40. In statement 1, “*a B2C e-commerce platform can increase your sales in this pandemic situation*” respondents strongly agreed with a weighted mean of 4.30. Respondents in statement 5, strongly agreed that “*the restaurant had been able to maintain its monthly sales by using B2C e-commerce*” with a weighted mean of 4.06.

Table 4. E-commerce's contribution to the restaurant industry's survival

Statements	Weighted Mean (N=105)	Verbal Interpretation
1. A B2C e-commerce platform can increase your sales in this pandemic situation.	4.30	Strongly Agree
2. Online market adoption is helpful for restaurants in this pandemic.	4.54	Strongly Agree
3. There are significant difference between online and physical sales in terms of dealing with the customers.	4.53	Strongly Agree
4. There is a substantial change in the restaurant's revenue in using digital technology.	4.40	Strongly Agree
5. The restaurant had been able to maintain its monthly sales by using B2C e-commerce.	4.06	Agree
6. It is important to recruit an employee that is flexible enough to do any task.	4.54	Strongly Agree

Table 5 shows that out of 105 respondents, in statement 4, "*Food and safety awareness to ensure food quality and quality service*" equates to a weighted mean of 4.73 which translates to strongly agree. Statement 1, "*Providing a user-friendly interface can help gain loyal customers*" equates to a weighted mean of 4.68 which translates to strongly agree. Statement 2, "*Improving the quality of content used in delivery apps helps attract more customers*" equates to a weighted mean of 4.63 which translates to strongly agree. In statement 3, "*Proper training for employees in using digital tools can improve a restaurant's productivity*" equates to a weighted mean of 4.63 which translates to strongly agree.

Table 5. Improvements to be made with the help of e-commerce

Statements	Weighted Mean (N=105)	Verbal Interpretation
1. Providing a user-friendly interface can help gain loyal customers.	4.68	Strongly Agree
2. Improving the quality of content used in delivery apps helps attract more customers.	4.63	Strongly Agree
3. Proper training for employees in using digital tools can improve a restaurant's productivity.	4.63	Strongly Agree
4. Food and safety awareness to ensure food quality and quality service.	4.73	Strongly Agree

Conclusion and Recommendations

The significance of this research is to show business-to-consumer e-commerce as one of the important factors for business owners. The views of high-ranking employees towards B2C e-commerce have been determined along with how B2C e-commerce help the casual dining restaurants cope and survive during the pandemic. This study aimed to provide valuable results that reflect business-to-consumer e-commerce in casual dining restaurants amidst the pandemic.

Based on the findings, casual dining restaurants in Bacoor can survive amidst this pandemic with the help of business-to-consumer e-commerce. Business-to-consumer e-commerce plays a huge part in surviving this pandemic. Restaurants suffer a significant loss of revenue because their operations are primarily based on face-to-face interaction. However, with the emergence of B2C e-commerce, they were able to sustain their businesses without having to consider temporarily closing them. They bring their service to their customers' homes rather than urging them to come to their restaurant.

The researchers recommend this study to future researchers with different types of research. Since the current study uses a quantitative research design, future researchers can acquire additional data by learning about the perceptions of participants about the role of business-to-consumer e-commerce in the restaurant industry amidst the COVID-19 pandemic through qualitative research. It is also important to note that this study was limited only to the Bacoor area and to a particular type of restaurant, namely casual dining. Furthermore, if the timeline shifts from pandemic to post-pandemic, researchers may be able to gain new insights.

Future researchers can determine whether B2C e-commerce usage was still prevalent during the post-pandemic period. A broader research scope may have led to additional findings. Since based on the assessment of the statement "*Selling through the internet requires low expenditures*" is interpreted as "agreed", the researchers recommend that restaurant owners review their cost of food and online service. Also, restaurants should innovate the use of B2C e-commerce since this platform was heavily used during this new normal setting and the majority "agreed" that using B2C e-commerce can maintain monthly sales. This research still has room for improvement depending on the changes in situations in the restaurant industry. Related research has already been cited, ensuring that it will all be of great assistance in conducting a similar study.

This study revolves around the general topic which is the increased digital adoption. However, the researchers specifically focused on business-to-consumer e-commerce in casual dining restaurants in Bacoor. About 148 restaurants use B2C e-commerce in Bacoor which is the only coverage of the study. The respondents were high-ranking employees such as managers and supervisors because they are the ones who are experiencing and implementing the adjustments in restaurants. They were also the ones who have access to information like sales reports, inventory reports, and customer relationship management (CRM) reports. Other sources were not treated as results aside from the findings acquired in a survey questionnaire sent to the target respondents.

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